
81. Supernova remnants

IN MY PREVIOUS essay (#80) I looked at Gaia’s ongoing contributions to the study of neutron stars, and in particular to the study of pulsars (their rapidly spinning, highly-magnetised manifestations) and, amongst them, to the occurrence of pulsars in orbital binary systems.

As I described there, pulsars are the dense, compact, collapsed cores of massive stars ($8 - 40M_{\odot}$), which result from a supernova explosion, with the most rapidly spinning ‘millisecond pulsars’ resulting from mass and angular momentum transfer from a binary companion.

Since a companion star can be ‘flung out’ during the impulsive burst of the supernova explosion, another important route to the study of neutron stars and pulsars is by searching for high-velocity stars receding from the sites of known supernova explosions. Enter astrometry!

A SUPERNOVA REMNANT is the prominent structure resulting from a supernova explosion. The explosion expels much of the remaining stellar material at velocities up to 10% of the speed of light. At these highly supersonic speeds, a strong shock wave forms ahead of the ejecta, heating the ambient interstellar medium to millions of degrees Kelvin. The shock slows as it sweeps up material, but it can expand over centuries, and tens of parsecs, before it slows to below the local sound speed.

Of the 295 supernova remnants catalogued by Green, prominent examples include the Crab Nebula (discovered in 1731, and associated with a supernova recorded by Chinese astronomers in 1054); Tycho (SN 1572, named after Tycho Brahe who recorded its original explosion); Kepler (SN 1604, named after Johannes Kepler); Cas A (from around 1667, in the constellation Cassiopeia, and one of the brightest radio sources); the 40 000-yr old Spaghetti Nebula (discovered in 1952); SN 1987A (a young supernova in the Large Magellanic Cloud observed in February 1987); and G1.9+0.3 (the youngest known in our Galaxy, discovered in 2008).

Of their remnant pulsars, only the Crab pulsar (16.5 mag) is bright enough at optical wavelengths to be observable directly by Gaia. Only a handful of others have known optical emission, the next brightest being PSR B0540–69 (23 mag), and the Vela pulsar (23.6 mag).

PROVIDING A THEORETICAL framework for search programmes, Renzo et al. (2019) estimated that 20–30% of massive binary systems merge prior to the supernova event and, of the remainder, some 80–90% become unbound. Only a minority of those ejected are ‘runaways’ (loosely defined as velocities above 30 km s^{-1}), with the majority having much lower velocities.

Various searches have been made for these surviving binary companions of massive stars which exploded as supernovae within our Galaxy, focused on finding escaping stars ‘pointing back’ to nearby supernova remnants.

MUCH MORE comprehensive searches are now possible using the Gaia astrometry. Using Gaia Data Release 2, Fraser & Boubert (2019) made an extensive search for surviving binary companions to three of the best-studied supernova remnants in our Galaxy.

Consistent with previous work, they found no plausible binary companion to either the Crab or Cas A supernovae. Examining nearly 80 000 Gaia sources within a 0.5 degree radius, they also ruled out any luminous ($L > L_{\odot}$) companion to the Vela supernova, while noting a faint kinematic companion more likely to be a background star. They concluded that none of these supernovae had a stellar companion at the time of explosion.

THE DISTANCE TO the Crab pulsar and its supernova remnant is still only poorly known, although it is widely assumed to be around 1.93 kpc (Trimble, 1973).

Fraser & Boubert (2019) derived a significantly larger distance, $3.37^{+4.04}_{-0.97}$ kpc, based on the Gaia DR2 parallax, with implications for models of its underlying pulsar physics.

They also showed that Gaia’s multi-epoch photometry already hints at a measurable secular decrease of the pulsar’s luminosity. Being attributed to synchrotron radiation losses, this will also provide new constraints on models of pulsar physics.

HIGH-VELOCITY ‘runaway stars’ are not only generated in binary supernova events, but also by ejection following the gravitational interaction of stars in dense stellar systems, such as globular clusters or stellar associations. A supernova origin would be invoked if the runaway star’s trajectory could be traced back to the position of the supernova remnant (or to its common origin with the remaining neutron star), and further supported (for example) if supernova debris can be identified in the runaway star’s atmosphere via high-resolution spectroscopy (e.g. Przybilla et al., 2008).

Using the astrometry of Gaia DR2, Neuhäuser et al. (2020) examined the 68 pulsars with known transverse velocities in the Scorpius–Centaurus–Lupus association. Amongst other results, they connected the runaway star ζ Oph to the radio pulsar PSR B1706–16, tracing both objects back to a common origin 1.78 ± 0.21 Myr ago. They also argued that the moderate distance of the implied supernova, 107 ± 4 pc, makes it likely that this event contributed to the ^{60}Fe deposit that has been detected in the Earth’s crust and ocean sediments, and attributed to such a recent nearby supernova (e.g. Knie et al. 1999).

PREVIOUS SEARCHES for this type of runaway star have generally been restricted to luminous O and B type stars because of their young ages, and their detectability out to large distances. The comprehensive Gaia data now makes this type of large-scale search feasible for runaway stars of *all* spectral types. Spectroscopy of any candidates can hope to verify their young ages by means of the standard ‘lithium test’.

Lux et al. (2021) made such a search for 12 nearby supernova remnants, including Vela, Puppis A, and the Cygnus Loop. For each, they selected all Gaia stars brighter than 17 mag within a search radius defined by the remnant’s age and distance. They then traced back the projected trajectories of each, using their proper motions and the age of the supernova remnant, to obtain their coordinates at the time of the supernova explosion.

Of their 12 selected supernova remnants, they excluded runaway stars brighter than 17 mag in three, confirmed the previously known candidate HD 37424 in Simeis 147 (G180.0–01.7, the ‘Spaghetti Nebula’) and, from high-resolution spectra of 39 stars, found one or more candidates in each of the remaining eight. Three of these supernovae could possibly have ejected two runaway stars. Further confirmation of these possible candidates will require higher resolution spectroscopy.

A SIMILAR SEARCH of 10 supernova remnants (with many of the targets in common with the study by Lux et al., 2021), but now based on Gaia EDR3, was made by Kochanek (2021). He confirmed the one known example of an unbound binary, HD 37424 in G180.0–01.7, but found no other examples.

The fraction of stars that are in binary or triple systems at the time of a supernova explosion, and the fraction of these companions that survive the explosion, provide crucial constraints for evolution models and predictions for gravitational wave source populations. Kochanek (2021) concluded (for example) that 72% of supernovae producing neutron stars are not binaries at the time of explosion, 14% produce bound binaries, and 12.5% produce unbound binaries.

Incidentally, one of his target supernova remnants, G039.7–02.0 (W50) contains the exotic system SS 433: an eclipsing X-ray binary, with the primary being a stellar-mass black hole, and its relativistic precession resulting in both blue and red Doppler shifts at visible wavelengths. As another example of the present Gaia astrometry being at odds with the pre-Gaia consensus, the distance to SS 433 implied by the Gaia EDR3 parallax (6.1 – 13.9 kpc) disagrees with estimates from kinematic models of its jets, viz. around 5.5 ± 0.2 kpc (Blundell & Bowler, 2004) or 4.5 ± 0.2 kpc (Marshall et al., 2013).

MY FINAL EXAMPLE of the application of Gaia data to the understanding of supernova remnants relates to our present understanding of the formation of stellar mass black holes. While observations of interacting black hole binaries, as well as the LIGO gravitational wave results, provide clear evidence that stellar-mass black holes exist, there appears to be no immediate prospect of directly investigating their formation. Meanwhile, modern theoretical models suggest that some 10–30% of stellar core collapses fail to result in a supernova, and instead become black holes.

This led Kochanek et al. (2008) to propose a search for failed supernovae by looking for massive stars which suddenly ‘vanish’. In contrast to transient searches looking for the appearance of new sources such as supernovae, the idea is to do the opposite – to search for the disappearance of massive stars. With the systematic observation of nearby galaxies in order to monitor some million supergiants, such a disappearance should occur yearly, since these massive stars must end their lives through core collapse within about a million years.

Indeed, from monitoring with the Large Binocular Telescope and others, at least one such candidate has been identified, N6946–BH1 (Basinger et al. 2021). The $300000 L_{\odot}$ red supergiant progenitor underwent an outburst in 2009, and has since disappeared!

An alternative to searching for these individual progenitors is to use the local stellar population to infer the likely progenitor mass. Kochanek (2022) used the Gaia EDR3 parallaxes of luminous stars in the vicinity of the Vela pulsar to characterise a representative stellar population, starting with 37 000 stars within 250 pc of the pulsar. His analysis concluded that the Vela pulsar progenitor was of low mass, in the range 8.1 – $10.3 M_{\odot}$.